

Assessment of Effective Chemical Fungicide for Managing Spot Blotch Disease in Wheat

B. Hijam¹, G.L. Maharaja², A. Roy¹
and S. Hembram^{2*}

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jarvm.submit@gmail.com

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¹Department of Plant Pathology, ²Regional Research Station, Terai Zone, Uttar Banga Krishi Viswavidyalaya, Pundibari, Cooch Behar, West Bengal (736 165), India.

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ABSTRACT

A field experiment was conducted from November 2022 to March 2023 at the University Research Farm, Uttar Banga Krishi Viswavidyalaya, Pundibari, West Bengal, to evaluate the efficacy of eight chemical fungicides for managing spot blotch disease in wheat caused by *Bipolaris sorokiniana*. The experiment included systemic and contact fungicides *viz.*, Propiconazole, Tebuconazole, Mancozeb, Carbendazim, and their combinations. The wheat variety RAJ 4015, highly susceptible to spot blotch, was used under a randomized block design. The pathogen was isolated, purified, and mass-multiplied for artificial inoculation. Fungicides were applied twice at heading and anthesis stages. Disease progress was monitored, and data on disease severity, AUDPC (Area Under Disease Progress Curve), percent disease reduction index (PDRI), percent increase in yield (PIY), and benefit-cost (B: C) ratio were recorded. All the fungicide treatments significantly reduced disease severity compared to the untreated control. The combination of Propiconazole 13.9% + Difenconazole 13.9% proved most effective, resulting in the lowest AUDPC (476), highest PDRI (49.82%), and PIY (52%). However, sole Propiconazole 25% EC recorded the highest B: C ratio (1.37), suggesting greater economic viability despite slightly lower disease suppression. The findings indicated that while Propiconazole + Difenconazole offered superior disease control and yield enhancement, Propiconazole 25% EC emerged as the most cost-effective option for integrated spot blotch management in wheat.

Keywords: Wheat, *Bipolaris sorokiniana*, spot blotch, fungicides, AUDPC, disease management.

*Corresponding Author:

S. Hembram

Regional Research Station,
Terai Zone, Uttar Banga Krishi
Viswavidyalaya, Pundibari,
Cooch Behar, West Bengal
(736 165), India.

1. Introduction

Wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) had served as one of the most important staple food crops globally, feeding nearly 55% of the world's population and contributing about 20% to daily caloric intake. It ranked second among cereal crops in both area and production. During the 2024-25 marketing year, global wheat production was estimated at approximately 793 million metric tonnes (Statista, 2025). India, position the second-largest wheat producer following China (Anonymous, 2024), with total production projected at 122.724 million tonnes as of March 31, 2025 (Anonymous, 2025).

Despite all such achievements, a significant decline in the wheat cultivation area had been observed across several Indian states in recent years. West Bengal experienced the sharpest drop at 64.24%, followed by Maharashtra and Telangana (Anonymous, 2018). This decline was primarily attributed to multiple biotic and abiotic stresses, among which diseases played a major role in reducing yields. Of the more than 200 known diseases, nearly 50 were considered economically important (Jarroudi et al., 2017). It was estimated that globally, diseases caused around 20% loss in wheat production annually (Al-Sadi, 2021). In India, the average yield loss due to spot blotch was reported to be between 18–22%, but could potentially reached up to 87% under severe conditions on susceptible varieties (Gupta et al., 2018; Singh et al., 2023; Hijam et al., 2025).

Among them the most devastating diseases was spot blotch, caused by *Bipolaris sorokiniana* (teleomorph *Cochliobolus sativus*), a necrotrophic fungal pathogen. The disease thrived in warm, humid environments and was widely prevalent in the Eastern Gangetic Plains, encompassing parts of India, Nepal, and Bangladesh (Gupta et al., 2018; Patsa et al., 2018). The pathogen affected multiple parts of the wheat plant, including leaves, stems, sheaths, and glumes. Disease severity increased sharply under high temperature and humidity during the grain-filling stage, especially in susceptible cultivars, leading to significant

losses in both yield and grain quality (Saari, 1998).

The North Eastern Plains Zone of India, including the northern districts of West Bengal, exhibited particularly favourable conditions for the development and spread of spot blotch, especially in late-sown wheat crops. While earlier studies had estimated yield losses due to the disease at 18-22% (Singh and Srivastava, 1997), more recent reports suggested that for every 1% increase in disease severity, yield loss could range from 1.8-2.0 kg ha⁻¹, and 1000-grain weight could decrease by 0.89-1.59 g (Devi et al., 2017). The disease was reported to affect about 25 million hectares globally, with nearly 40% of that area located in South Asia (Joshi et al., 2007). In highly susceptible cultivars, yield losses had reached up to 87%, while in West Bengal, losses of up to 43% had been recorded (Chowdhury et al., 2008).

Although the development of resistant wheat varieties was considered the most sustainable solution, existing commercial cultivars often lacked sufficient resistance to prevent yield and quality deterioration (Gupta et al., 2018). Cultural practices such as crop rotation, clean cultivation, and summer ploughing offered partial relief but failed to manage the disease once it had established in the field. Biological control methods, though environmentally friendly, remained inconsistent due to variable climatic conditions. Consequently, chemical fungicides continued to serve as the most widely adopted and practical strategy for managing spot blotch in Indian agriculture.

Several fungicides, including Propiconazole, Tebuconazole, Mancozeb, and Azoxystrobin, had demonstrated promising results in field trials (Singh et al., 2011; Kumar et al., 2021). However, their comparative effectiveness and economic viability under endemic conditions warranted further investigation. The present study was undertaken to evaluate the efficacy of selected systemic and contact fungicides for managing spot blotch disease in wheat under the Agro-climatic conditions of northern West Bengal.

2. Material and Methods

The field experiment was conducted during the rabi season from November 2022 to March 2023 at the University Research Farm of Uttar Banga Krishi Viswavidyalaya, Pundibari, Cooch Behar, West Bengal. Wheat (cv. RAJ 4015), known for its high susceptibility to spot blotch disease, was sown in November and harvested in March. The experimental design followed a Randomized Block Design (RBD), with a total plot area of 14×50 m², divided into three rows, each segmented into eight plots. Each plot contained six rows of wheat, spaced 20 cm apart, with 70 cm wide alleyways after every six rows to facilitate management and observations.

Fertilization was done at a rate of 150:60:60 kg ha⁻¹ (N: P: K), with full doses of phosphorus and potassium and half of the nitrogen applied at sowing. The remaining nitrogen was top-dressed at 30 and 60 days after sowing (DAS). Sowing was carried manually in furrows created with a hand hoe. Irrigation was scheduled at 21, 52-55, 72-75, and 92-110 DAS. Manual weeding and selective herbicide applied as per the requirement to maintain weed-free plots.

2.1. Isolation and Purification of Pathogen

Leaf samples showing characteristic spot blotch symptoms were collected from infected plants in the experimental plots. The infected tissues (5×5 mm segments from lesion margins) were surface sterilized using 1% sodium hypochlorite for 30-45 seconds, rinsed thrice in sterile distilled water, and blotted dry. The segments were placed on Potato Dextrose Agar (PDA) plates and slants under aseptic conditions and incubated at $25 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ in a BOD chamber. Pure cultures of *Bipolaris sorokiniana* were established through hyphal tip transfer.

2.2. Single spore isolation

To obtain monoconidial cultures, mycelial bits were suspended in 10 ml sterile distilled water, and the spore concentration was adjusted using serial dilution. A 500 µl aliquot was spread on water agar plates and incubated for 24 hours at $25 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$. Individual germinated spores were identified under a microscope and transferred to

fresh PDA plates for pure culture development.

2.3. Inoculum Preparation and Application

Approximately 500 g of wheat grains were washed, dried, and equally distributed into 250 ml conical flasks. After adding minimal water, the flasks were sealed with cotton plugs and autoclaved. Once cooled, they were inoculated with pure *B. sorokiniana* cultures and incubated at $28 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ for 15-20 days for sporulation. The sporulated grain culture was filtered through muslin cloth, and the spore concentration was adjusted to 10^4 spores/ml using distilled water. The spore suspension was sprayed twice over the plots using a hand atomizer during the late evening, starting 7-8 days before the booting stage, targeting the flag leaf emergence stage.

2.4. Fungicide application

To manage spot blotch, eight chemical fungicides, both systemic and non-systemic, were tested. These included propiconazole, tebuconazole, mancozeb, and various combinations such as Propiconazole+ Difenconazole, Azoxystrobin+ Difenconazole, Azoxystrobin+ Tebuconazole, and Picoxystrobin+ Propiconazole (Table 1). The fungicides were applied twice: the first application at the heading stage (seven days after inoculation), followed by a second application at the anthesis stage (9-10 days later). The field was regularly monitored to assess disease development and evaluate fungicidal effectiveness.

2.5. Disease Assessment

The disease severity data were recorded every 7 days from the first incidence of the disease. The disease was recorded from the last week of February till the mid-week of March. Harvesting was done in April. 10 plants were randomly selected from each plot after the flowering stage and were tagged; the disease scoring was done on these 10 plants. Disease severity was recorded and scored using the double disease scale (00-99) (Saari and Prescott, 1998; Eyal et al., 1987; Kumar et al., 1998) based on the total leaf area covered with the lesions.

2.6. Harvesting and Yield Measurement

Upon maturity of the plants, harvesting and threshing were carried separately for each plot and the number of grains per panicle and plot yield were recorded. For the determination of the test weight, 1000 kernels were randomly

counted and weighed. Finally, the yield of each plot was converted to tonnes per hectare. The percent increase in yield and avoidable yield loss were also calculated by using the following formula given by Patel et al. (2021),

$$\text{Percent increase in yield} = \frac{\text{Yield in treated plot} - \text{Yield in controlled plot}}{\text{Yield in controlled plot}} \times 100$$

$$\text{Avoidable yield losses} = \frac{YP - YU}{YP} \times 100$$

where, YP = Yield under protected condition; YU = Yield under unprotected condition

Table 1. Fungicides used for the management of *Bipolaris sorokiniana*

Treatment	Chemical name	Trade name
T1	Propiconazole 13.9%+Difenoconazole 13.9%	Nativo (Bayer)
T2	Azoxystrobin 18.2%+Difenoconazole 11.11% SC	Amistertop (Syngent)
T3	Azoxystrobin 11%+Tebuconazole 18.3%	Custodia (Adama)
T4	Picoxystrobin 7.05%+Propiconazole 11.7%	Galileo Way (DUPON)
T5	Propiconazole 25%	Tilt (Syngenta)
T6	Tebuconazole 25.9%	Orius (Adama)
T7	Mancozeb 75%WP	Indofil M-45 (Indofil)
T8	Carbedazim 50%WP	Bavistin(Crystal)
T9	Control	-----

Table 2. FRAC codes of the fungicides used in the management of Spot Blotch of Wheat

Fungicides used	Group or Chemical name	Target Site	Comments	FRAC code
Propiconazole, Difenoconazole, Tebuconazole	Triazoles	Demethylation inhibitors	Medium risk	3
Azoxystrobin, Picoxystrobin	QoI Fungicides	Inhibition of the cytochrome bc 1 complex	High risk	11
Mancozeb	Dithiocarbamates	Multi-site contact action	Low risk	M-03
Carbendazim	Benzimidazoles	Inhibition of beta tubulin polymerization	High risk	1

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The present study assessed the efficacy of eight fungicidal treatments, including systemic, contact, and combination fungicides, in the management of spot blotch disease of wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.) caused by *Bipolaris*

sorokiniana under field conditions in the Terai agro-climatic zone of northern West Bengal during the 2022-23 rabi season. Based on Table 2, the fungicides used in the study belonged to different FRAC groups with distinct modes of action and resistance risks. Triazoles (Group 3),

including Propiconazole, Difenoconazole, and Tebuconazole, act as demethylation inhibitors with medium resistance risk. QoIs like Azoxystrobin and Picoxystrobin (Group 11) target mitochondrial respiration and carry a high resistance risk. Carbendazim (Group 1) also has a high resistance risk due to its single-site action, while Mancozeb (Group M-03) offers low risk due to its multi-site contact activity. These classifications emphasize the need to include fungicides with different FRAC codes to delay the fungicides resistance and maintain long-term efficacy. The superior performance of triazole-strobilurin combinations such as T2 and T3 can be explained by their dual mode of action—strobilurins inhibit mitochondrial respiration by targeting the cytochrome *bcl* complex (FRAC group 11), while triazoles inhibit ergosterol biosynthesis (FRAC group 3). This dual mechanism increases efficacy and delays resistance development (Fernandez-Ortuno et al., 2020). However, the results also highlighted the need for judicious fungicide uses to minimize resistance risks, especially with QoI fungicides like azoxystrobin, which have a high resistance potential (FRAC, 2024). Adoption of integrated disease management (IDM) practices, including cultivar resistance, crop rotation, and timely fungicide application, is crucial for sustaining wheat health under

changing climatic conditions (Jesumaharaja et al., 2023).

The results indicated that all fungicidal treatments significantly reduced disease severity and improved grain yield compared to the untreated control. Disease severity was recorded using a 00-99 scale and quantified over time using the area under the disease progress curve (AUDPC). Among the treatments (Table 1), the combination of Propiconazole 13.9% + Difenoconazole 13.9% SC (T1) recorded the lowest AUDPC value of 476, indicating the most effective disease suppression (Table 3). This was followed by Picoxystrobin 7.05% + Propiconazole 11.7% SC (T4; AUDPC = 573.58), Azoxystrobin 11% + Tebuconazole 18.3% SC (T3; AUDPC = 579.42), and Azoxystrobin 18.2% + Difenoconazole 11.11% SC (T2; AUDPC = 642.03). These treatments significantly outperformed the control (T9), which showed the highest AUDPC of 948.65. The superior performance of T1 could be attributed to the complementary action of triazoles, which inhibit ergosterol biosynthesis, essential for fungal membrane integrity (Zhang et al., 2010). Similar trends were reported by Singh et al. (2011) and Kumar et al. (2021), who found that propiconazole-based treatments substantially reduced foliar blight severity and delayed disease onset.

Table 3. Effect of chemical fungicides in the management of spot blotch in wheat

Treatments	Fungicides	AUDPC	Percent reduction in disease index (PDRI)	Yield	Percent increase in yield (PIY)
T1	Propiconazole 13.9%+ Difenoconazole 13.9% SC	476	49.82	3.80	52
T2	Azoxystrobin 18.2%+ Difenoconazole 11.11% SC	642.03	32.32	3.40	36
T3	Azoxystrobin 11%+Tebuconazole 18.3% SC	579.42	38.92	3.30	32
T4	Picoxystrobin 7.05%+ Propiconazole 11.7% SC	573.58	39.54	3.60	44
T5	Propiconazole 25% EC	731.93	22.85	3.70	48

T6	Tebuconazole 25.9% EC	747.97	21.15	3.10	24
T7	Mancozeb 75% WP	771.44	18.68	2.90	16
T8	Carbendazim 50% WP	826.76	12.85	2.80	12
T9	Control	948.65	-	2.50	-

Different letters indicate significant difference at 0.05% level of significance

The percent disease reduction index (PDRI) mirrored the AUDPC results. T1 showed the highest PDRI of 49.82%, followed by T4 (39.54%), T3 (38.92%), and T2 (32.32%). In contrast, Mancozeb 75% WP (T7) and Carbendazim 50% WP (T8) recorded lower PDRI of 18.68% and 12.85%, respectively (Table 3), indicating limited efficacy under field conditions. These findings align with those of Yadav et al. (2013), who reported reduced effectiveness of contact fungicides like mancozeb against foliar diseases in humid environments. Grain yield also reflected the effectiveness of treatments. T1 resulted in the highest yield of 3.80 t/ha, representing a 52% increase over the untreated control (2.50 t/ha). T5 (Propiconazole 25% EC) and T4 were also effective, yielding 3.70 t/ha and 3.60 t/ha, respectively. Similar yield improvements following propiconazole application were reported by Rashid et al. (2001) in Bangladesh and by Kumar et al. (2021) in the northern Eastern plains of India.

Table 4. Cost-benefit ratio of the different chemical fungicides in the management of spot blotch in wheat

TREATMENTS	Dose (ml or g/ha) (1)	Cost of chemical (Rs.) (2)	Cost of chemical /ha for 2 spray (Rs.) (3)	Cost of cultivation /ha (Rs.) (4)	Total cost (Rs) (5=3+4)	Total yield (t/ha) (6)	Gross Return (@28000/t) (7)	Net Returns (8=7-5) (5)	BC Ratio (9=8/5) ()
Propiconazole 13.9%+ Difenoconazole 13.9% SC	500	11400/L	5,700	43,000	48,700	3.8	106400	57700	1.18
Azoxystrobin 18.2%+ Difenoconazole 11.11% SC	500	4614/L	2,307	43,000	45,307	3.4	95200	49893	1.10
Azoxystrobin 11%+ Tebuconazole 18.3% SC	500	6320/L	3,160	43,000	46,160	3.3	92400	46240	1.00
Picoxystrobin 7.05%+ Propiconazole 11.7% SC	500	5500/L	2,750	43,000	45,750	3.6	100800	55050	1.20
Propiconazole 25% EC	500	1340/L	670	43,000	43,670	3.7	103600	59930	1.37
Tebuconazole 25.9% EC	500	2254/L	1,127	43,000	44,127	3.1	86800	42673	0.97
Mancozeb 75% WP	1000	486/kg	972	43,000	43,972	2.9	81200	37228	0.85
Carbendazim 50% WP	1000	2000/kg	4,000	43,000	47,000	2.8	78400	31400	0.67
Control	0	0	0	43,000	43,000	2.5	70000	27000	0.63

Though T1 recorded the best biological performance, T5 (Propiconazole 25% EC) provided the highest benefit-cost (B:C) ratio of 1.37 (Table 4), compared to 1.18 for T1. The economic advantage of T5 was due to its lower input cost (Rs. 670/ha) and relatively high yield gain. These findings suggest that while combination fungicides like T1 are highly effective in disease suppression, single active ingredient formulations like T5 offer a more economical option for farmers, particularly under resource-limited conditions. Previous studies by Gupta et al. (2020) and Singh et al. (2023) also emphasized the dual importance of efficacy and economic viability when selecting fungicidal treatments for spot blotch management. Furthermore, the results support the recommendation of integrating triazole-based fungicides, especially propiconazole, into regional disease management programs.

4. CONCLUSION

The study demonstrated that Propiconazole 13.9% + Difenconazole 13.9% SC was the most effective fungicidal combination for managing spot blotch, achieving the lowest AUDPC and highest yield increase. However, Propiconazole 25% EC offered the best cost-benefit ratio, making it a more feasible recommendation for farmers. These findings reinforce the role of triazole-based fungicides in integrated spot blotch management strategies in the eastern Indo-Gangetic plains.

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6. CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declared no conflict of interest.

7. REFERENCES

1. Al-Sadi, A.M., 2016. Variation in resistance to spot blotch and the aggressiveness of *Bipolaris sorokiniana* on barley and wheat cultivars. *Journal of Plant Pathology*. 98, 97-103. doi:10.4454/JPP.V98I1.029.
2. Anonymous., 2024. Fungicide Resistance Action Committee Code List. Available at: <https://www.frac.info>.
3. Anonymous., 2025. Wheat Crop Area and Production Estimation in India: A Pilot on Framework Development https://www.isro.gov.in/Wheat_Crop_Area_and_Production_Estimation_in_India.html#:~:text=The%20total%20Wheat%20production%20from,Figure%205a%20and%20Figure%205b.
4. Chowdhury, A.K., Mukherjee, S., Bandyopadhyay, S., Das, J. and Mondal, N.C., 2008. Resistance to *Helminthosporium* leaf blight and biochemical responses of wheat genotypes of diverse origins. *Journal of Mycopathological Research*, 46 (1): 59 – 63.
5. Devi, D., 2017. Studies on the variation of the pathogen causing spot blotch of wheat and different traits of the host related to its resistance. Ph.D. thesis dissertation work. Department of Plant Pathology, Uttar Banga Krishi Viswavidyalaya, cooch behar, India, 130p.
6. Eyal, Z., Scharen, A.L. and Prescott, J.M., 1987. The septoria diseases of wheat: Concepts and methods of disease management. Mexico, DF: CIMMYT. ISBN: 968-6127-06-2.
7. Fernandez-Ortuno, D., Tores, J.A., De Vicente, A., & Perez-Garcia, A., 2020. Mechanisms of resistance to QoI fungicides in phytopathogenic fungi. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*, 21(17), 6123. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms21176123>.
8. Gupta, P.K., Chand, R., Vasistha, N.K., Pandey, S.P., Kumar, U., Mishra, V.K., and Joshi, A.K., 2018. Spot blotch disease of

- wheat: the current status of research on genetics and breeding. *Plant Pathology*. 67 (3) :508-531. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ppa.12781>.
9. Gupta, S.K., Basnet, R., Pant, K.J., Wagle, P. and Bhatta, M., 2020. Efficacy of chemical and organic fungicides against spot blotch management of wheat. *Journal of plant sciences and crop protection*. 2(2): ISSN: 2639-3336.
 10. Hijam, B., Maharaja, G. L., Roy, A., Roy, V. and Hembram, S., 2025. Assessment of Some Culture Media for Optimum Growth and Sporulation of *Bipolaris sorokiniana* Causing Spot Blotch of Wheat. *International Journal of Economic Plants*. 12(1), 01-06. <https://doi.org/10.23910/2/2025.5703a>.
 11. <https://www.frac.info/fungicide-resistance-management/by-frac-mode-of-action-group#open-tour>
 12. Jarroudi, M.E., Kouadio, L., Bock, C. H., Junk, J., Pasquali, M., Maraite, H., 2017. A threshold-based weather model for predicting stripe rust infection in winter wheat. *Plant Disease*. 101, 693–703. doi: 10.1094/pdis-12-16-1766-re. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/30678577/>
 13. Jesumaharaja, G.L., Dhar, A., Bhaumik, P., Yonzone, R., Debnath, M.K., Dinesh, Kumar, P., Ahila, Devi, P., and Hembram, S., 2023. Assessment of Emerging Wheat Diseases in Northern Region of West Bengal under a changing climate scenario. *Biological forum: an international journal*. 15 (12), 329-34. <https://www.researchtrend.net/bfij/pdf/>.
 14. Joshi, A.K., Mishra, B., Chatrath, R., Ortiz Ferrara, G. and Singh, R.P., 2007. Wheat improvement in India: present status, emerging challenges and future prospects. *Euphytica*. 157: 431-446. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s10681-007-9385-7>.
 15. Kumar, J., Singh, G. and Nagarajan, S. (1998). A field scale of leaf blight recording. *Indian Wheat News Newsletter*, 5(2): pp 3-4.
 16. Kumar, V., Kumar, G., Azad, C.S., Kumar, A., Raj, M., 2021. Impact of fungicides on *Bipolaris sorokiniana* causing spot blotch disease of wheat under in vitro and in vivo conditions. *Biological Forum- An International Journal*, 13(3a): 441-447. www.researchtrend.net/bfij.
 17. Patel, S.S., Singh, S.P., Kumar, S., Patel, A.K., Singh, D., 2021. *In-vivo* Management of Spot Blotch (*Bipolaris sorokiniana*) of Wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.), using Bio-Agent and Fungicides. *International Journal of Current Microbiology and Applied Sciences*. 10(01): 3339-3346. doi: <https://doi.org/10.20546/ijemas.2021.1001.392>.
 18. Patsa, R., Hembram, S., Bhattacharya, P.M., Bandyopadhyay, S., Dutta, S., 2018. Performance of different wheat genotypes on the occurrence of spot blotch disease and yield under varying dates of sowing. *Journal of Mycology Plant Pathology*. 48(4), 417-427. www.researchgate.net/publication/331199681
 19. Rashid, AQMB., Sarker, K., Khalequzzaman, K.M. 2001. Control of *Bipolaris* leaf blight of wheat with foliar spray of Tilt 250 Ec. *Bangladesh Journal of Plant Pathology*. 2001; 17: 45-47.
 20. Saari, E.E., 1998. Leaf blight disease and associated soil-borne fungal pathogens of wheat in South and Southeast Asia. Duvellier, E., et al, (eds). *Helminthosporium* blights of wheat: spot blotch and tan spot. CIMMYT, Mexico D.F., 37-51. https://books.google.co.in/books?id=ISr137u dgkC&pg=PA37&source=gbstoc_r&cad=2#v=onepage&q&f=false.
 21. Singh, C.K., Singh, C., Singh, D., Singh, R.K., Chaudhary, A.K., Kumar, R.R., 2023. Effect of chemicals and bioagents on spot blotch disease of wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.). *International Journal of Bioresource and*

- Stress Management. 7(4), 712-715.
<https://ojs.pphouse.org/index.php/IJBSM/article/view/954>.
22. Singh, D.V., Srivastava, K.D., 1997. Foliar blights and *Fusarium* scab of wheat. Present status and strategies for management. In: Management of threatening plant diseases of national importance. Malhotra Publishing House, New Delhi. pp. 1-16.
opac.narc.gov.np › [opac_css](#) › [index](#).
23. Singh, S.K., Srivastava, K.D., Aggarwal, R., Singh, V.B., 2011. Control of spot blotch (*Bipolaris sorokiniana*) of wheat using systemic fungicides. Indian Phytopathology. 64(1):82-84.
24. Statista., 2025. Global wheat production from 1990/1991 to 2024/2025 (in million metric tons).
<https://www.statista.com/statistics/267268/production-of-wheat-worldwide-since-1990/>.
25. Yadav, B., Singh, R., Kumar, A., 2013. Effect of micronutrients and fungicides on spot blotch of wheat. Vegetos 26, 212–219.
doi: 10.5958/j.2229-4473.26.2.077.
26. Zhang, Y.J., Zhang, X., Chen, C.J., Zhou, M.G., Wang, H.C., 2010. Effects of fungicides JS399-19, azoxystrobin, tebuconazole and carbendazim on the physiological and biochemical indices and grain yield of winter wheat. Pesticide Biochemistry and Physiology 98:151-157.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pestbp.2010.04.007>
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